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4 **Title**

5 Disentangling diverse responses to climate change among global marine ecosystem models

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55

56 **Abstract**

57 Climate change is warming the ocean and impacting lower trophic level (LTL) biomass and
58 production. Marine ecosystem models can provide projections of how climate change will
59 impact societal services such as fisheries, but these estimates vary widely. A better
60 understanding of what drives this variation will improve our ability to project fisheries and
61 other ecosystem services into the future, while also helping to identify uncertainties in
62 process understanding. Here, we explore mechanisms driving the diversity of responses to
63 changes in temperature and LTLs in eight global marine ecosystem models from the Fisheries
64 and Marine Ecosystem Model Intercomparison Project (FishMIP). Temperature and LTL
65 impacts on total consumer biomass and ecosystem structure (defined as the relative change
66 of small and large organism biomass) were isolated using a comparative experimental
67 protocol. Total model biomass varied between -35% to +3% in response to warming, and -
68 17% to +15% in response to LTL changes. There was little consensus about the spatial
69 redistribution of biomass or changes in the balance between small and large organisms
70 (ecosystem structure) in response to warming, and LTL impacts on total consumer biomass
71 varied depending on the choice of LTL forcing terms. Overall, climate change impacts on
72 consumer biomass and ecosystem structure are well approximated by the sum of
73 temperature and LTL impacts, indicating an absence of nonlinear interaction between the

74 models' drivers. Our results highlight a lack of theoretical clarity about how to represent
75 fundamental ecological mechanisms, most importantly how temperature impacts scale from
76 individual to ecosystem level, and the need to better understand the two-way coupling
77 between LTL organisms and consumers. We finish by identifying future research needs to
78 strengthen global marine ecosystem modelling and improve projections of climate change
79 impacts.

80

81 **Keywords**

82 *Climatic change, modelling, fishery oceanography, marine ecology, FishMIP, structural*
83 *uncertainty*

84

85

86 **1. Introduction**

87 Water temperature and primary production play critical roles in marine processes. Higher
88 temperatures accelerate reaction rates, with consequences ranging from the molecular to
89 ecosystem scale, while primary production provides the fundamental source of energy for
90 almost all marine life (Brown et al. 2004; Chavez et al. 2011). Climate change impacts on both
91 water temperature and primary production will thus alter marine ecosystems in fundamental
92 ways (Pörtner et al. 2014). For example, a first-order expectation of these impacts is that
93 accelerated metabolic rates will consume energy more quickly in a warmer ocean, all else
94 being equal, so that less biomass could be supported by a given level of primary production
95 (Heneghan et al, 2019). Yet, ecosystem-level effects emerge from individual-level processes
96 and interactions, which could lead to nonlinear effects and changes in ecosystem structure,
97 while shifting thermal habitats may influence the distribution of species, transforming food-
98 webs to previously unknown states (Coll et al. 2020; Pinsky et al. 2020; Poloczanska et al.
99 2016).

100

101 There is a growing need to quantify and project climate change impacts on marine ecosystems
102 to motivate mitigation (Bryndum-Buchholz et al. 2020), provide insight into potential future
103 threats to food security (Barange et al. 2014; Blanchard et al. 2017a; Boyce et al. 2020), and
104 identify needs for biodiversity conservation (Brito-Morales et al. 2020; Waldron et al. 2020).
105 Thus, there has been a recent proliferation of spatially-explicit marine ecosystem models that
106 simulate higher trophic level biomass and ecosystem structure at regional and global scales,
107 driven by output from climate-ocean-biogeochemical models (Tittensor et al. 2018). These
108 ecosystem models differ significantly in their design, level of complexity and implementation,
109 reflecting different choices for how to represent fundamental marine ecosystem processes,

110 as well as a diversity of model purpose and scope. As a result, there is considerable
111 uncertainty in model projections of climate change impacts on higher trophic levels (e.g. Lotze
112 et al., 2019), with projections from each model dependent upon decisions around inclusion
113 or simplification of processes. Structural diversity in model projections is a strength for
114 gaining a rich view of possible outcomes, given that each model reflects a different subset of
115 established physiological and process knowledge, implemented using different mathematical
116 representations (Knutti, 2010; Brander et al. 2013; Lefevre et al. 2017; Payne et al. 2016). At
117 the same time, this diversity reflects fundamental uncertainty in our understanding of
118 processes. Thus, identifying sources of structural uncertainty in ensemble projections can
119 point to critical weaknesses and thereby accelerate model improvement.

120

121 The Fisheries and Marine Ecosystem Model Intercomparison Project (FishMIP) was created to
122 explore this uncertainty and provide more robust assessments of climate impacts on marine
123 ecosystems through the analysis of multi-model ensembles (Tittensor et al. 2018). A recent
124 FishMIP study (Lotze et al. 2019) found that projections of mean changes in animal biomass
125 from a model ensemble typically compared better with empirical data than individual models,
126 emphasising the benefits of ensemble climate impact projections. However, uncertainty in
127 ensemble projections of higher trophic level biomass is significant: Lotze et al. (2019) found
128 that the spread of changes across the FishMIP ensemble in 21st century marine consumer
129 biomass under the high emissions, representative concentration pathway 8.5 (RCP8.5)
130 climate change scenario (0 to -35%) was larger than the multi-model mean consumer biomass
131 change between the RCP2.6 (low emissions) and RCP8.5 scenarios (-5% to -20%). This means
132 that structural uncertainty across global marine models is greater than climate scenario

133 uncertainty, which is problematic for the goal of using these models to provide assessments
134 of climate impacts on marine ecosystems and the societal services they provide.

135

136 For all global models in the FishMIP ensemble, temperature and lower trophic level (LTL)
137 forcings such as net primary production, phytoplankton and zooplankton biomass, and export
138 carbon are the two main drivers of projected climate change impacts (Tittensor et al. 2018),
139 yet their implementations vary. Although there is some agreement on how temperature
140 impacts physiological processes in general (e.g. Kooijman, 2010), there is less agreement on
141 how these impacts vary across functional groups, body sizes, and different processes such as
142 growth and metabolism (van Denderen et al. 2020). Similarly, although it is universally
143 understood that LTL biomass and production provide the source of energy that supports
144 higher trophic levels, there is less understanding about how the physiology and structure of
145 LTLs affects transfer efficiency and ecosystem structure, and how to couple lower and higher
146 trophic levels (Eddy et al. 2020; Heneghan et al. 2016; Stock et al. 2017). Previous multi-model
147 ensemble studies have explored structural model uncertainty in projections of consumer
148 biomass and species distribution shifts under climate change (e.g. Jones et al. 2012;
149 Woodworth-Jefcoats et al. 2015), but these studies did not disentangle the effects of
150 temperature and lower trophic level (LTL) changes, a strategy that can provide mechanistic
151 insight on underlying processes (Carozza et al. 2018).

152

153 Here, we identify sources of structural uncertainty in marine ecosystem models, by
154 disentangling the effects of temperature and LTL changes on model projections using eight
155 global models from the FishMIP ensemble. We first summarise how temperature and LTL
156 processes are incorporated in these models, highlighting common representations and

157 differences across the ensemble. We then isolate the impact of changes in temperature and
158 LTL processes on consumer biomass and ecosystem structure (which we define as the relative
159 change in small <30 cm and large \geq 30 cm consumer biomass) in a simulation protocol
160 involving a combination of pre-industrial, historical and RCP8.5 forcings. By illuminating key
161 sources of structural uncertainty in marine model projections, we identify critical areas of
162 future research necessary to improve not only climate impact projections but also our
163 understanding of the marine ecosystem.

164

165 **2. Methods**

166 We used projections from eight marine ecosystem models from the Fisheries and marine
167 ecosystem Model Intercomparison Project (FishMIP, www.fishmip.org; Tittensor et al. 2018).

168 There are several model types (see Tables 1 and 2 for a summary of each model and key
169 references). First, models that draw on the strongly size-structured nature of marine
170 ecosystem processes to represent the ecosystem purely by body size (BOATS,
171 Macroecological) or trophic level (EcoTroph). Second, trait-based size-structured models
172 (APECOSM, DBPM, FEISTY, ZooMSS), which move beyond a purely size-based representation
173 to include different communities and groups using functional traits other than body size. Last,
174 DBEM is a habitat suitability-based species-distribution model that resolves the biomass and
175 spatial distribution of >1200 fish and invertebrate species using observational data, and
176 includes other mechanisms such as species ecophysiology and dispersal. There is large
177 variation in the structural complexity of the models, and a detailed description of how each
178 model incorporates temperature and lower trophic level (LTL) impacts, including relevant
179 equations and temperature parameters, can be found in the Supplementary Information S2.

180 Here we summarise the key similarities and differences of each model as they pertain to

181 temperature, LTLs and other drivers in Sections 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and Table 1 and 2. We then
182 explain the experimental protocol and model outputs in Section 2.4.

183

184 **2.1. How do models incorporate temperature impacts?**

185 Across all models, individuals gain mass through anabolic processes such as food uptake and
186 assimilation, while they lose mass through catabolic processes such as respiration.

187 Populations can also gain individuals through reproduction, and lose individuals through
188 mortality (Table 2). These processes are all influenced by temperature. As a result, changes

189 in ecosystem structure depend on how models resolve: (i) temperature effects on individual
190 anabolic and catabolic processes across different functional groups, body sizes or trophic

191 levels; and (ii) how these variations drive changes in ecological interactions (Table 2).

192 Temperature effects on these processes are represented in all models as an exponential
193 scaling, with parameters varying widely between models (Supplementary Information S2).

194 However, within models the same temperature scaling parameters are used across all
195 functional groups and ecosystem components, excluding EcoTroph, which uses different
196 scalings depending on the ecosystem's biome.

197

198 The representation of anabolic and catabolic processes varies across models (Table 2).

199 Macroecological and EcoTroph have the simplest representations, with individual mass
200 changes resolved implicitly in each model by a single individual metabolic rate that scales with

201 temperature and body size (for Macroecological) or trophic level (for EcoTroph). For these
202 models, total biomass at a given body size/trophic level is determined by the metabolic

203 carrying capacity of that size/trophic level, divided by the metabolic rate of individuals. In

204 these two models, individual metabolic rates increase with temperature while total metabolic

205 carrying capacity at a given body size/trophic level is determined by net primary production.
206 Thus, as warming drives an increase in individual metabolism, total biomass decreases even
207 if primary production remains constant. The BOATS model uses a similar framework to
208 Macroecological and EcoTroph to determine maximum supported biomass at each body size
209 class. However, in BOATS individual mortality is resolved separately and the growth of
210 individuals from one size class to the next is explicitly resolved. As temperatures rise,
211 individual growth rates in BOATS increase, increasing the speed of biomass flow from small
212 to large size classes, but also increasing mortality and reducing the maximum biomass that
213 can be supported at each body size. Taken together, these processes mean that warming
214 causes total biomass to decrease in BOATS.

215

216 Within BOATS, Macroecological and EcoTroph, ecological interactions such as predator-prey
217 encounters or predator-predator competition are not explicitly resolved. Thus, temperature
218 and LTL drivers do not explicitly change interactions among individuals. However, in BOATS
219 and Macroecological, all primary producers are represented by a single body size, which is
220 inversely related to temperature; as temperature increases, the single representative body
221 size of primary producers decreases according to an empirical equation. This in turn decreases
222 the production of higher trophic level organisms, as the number of trophic steps that net
223 primary production must be transferred through to reach any given body size increases.
224 However, since trophic transfer efficiency in these models is not temperature-dependent, an
225 increase in the number of trophic levels is not expected to change the ratio of small and large
226 organism biomass. In contrast, transfer efficiency decreases with warming in Ecotroph. This
227 means that warmer waters in Ecotroph will support relatively less biomass at high trophic
228 levels (large body sizes) than what they will at low trophic levels (small body sizes).

229

230 For trait-based models (APECOSM, DBPM, FEISTY and ZooMSS), individual growth is fuelled
231 by ingesting smaller organisms, with individual ingestion rates scaling with temperature and
232 body size. For APECOSM, DBPM and FEISTY this scaling is also modulated with the density of
233 prey. Thus, food uptake for individuals at one size is fuelled by predation of smaller size
234 individuals, and in some cases predators can compete with each other for the same prey.
235 These models also include other sources of mortality (destruction of population biomass).
236 APECOSM, DBPM and ZooMSS incorporate at least one size-dependent mortality term, and
237 FEISTY includes a single natural mortality term that is independent of body size. These
238 additional mortality sources increase with temperature (except for senescence mortality in
239 DBPM and natural mortality in FEISTY), causing population biomass to decrease with
240 increasing temperature. In FEISTY, maintenance costs increase faster with both body size and
241 temperature than do ingestion rates. APECOSM and FEISTY also explicitly resolve size and
242 temperature-dependent costs of maintaining existing biomass (metabolism). In these models,
243 as temperature increases, maintenance costs also increase, reducing the available energy for
244 growth and reproduction. If maintenance costs of existing biomass exceed energy intake from
245 ingestion, biomass decreases. As food becomes limited in APECOSM, ingestion rates scale
246 more slowly with temperature than maintenance costs, limiting the scope for new growth
247 and potentially inducing biomass to decrease as maintenance costs outpace ingestion.

248

249 In APECOSM, DBPM, FEISTY and ZooMSS, temperature affects anabolic and catabolic
250 processes differently across ecosystems, which has cascading effects on how the different
251 components of ecosystems (e.g. predators and preys) interact. In APECOSM, FEISTY and
252 ZooMSS for example, the scaling of maintenance costs (in APECOSM and FEISTY) and

253 senescence mortality (in APECOSM and ZoomSS) with body size and temperature mean that
254 large organisms are more vulnerable to warming compared to small organisms. Everything
255 else being equal, a warming-induced decrease in large organism biomass would reduce
256 predation mortality on smaller organisms, thus favouring small organisms in these models.

257

258 Unlike what happens in the size and trait-based models, anabolic and catabolic processes in
259 DBEM are not driven explicitly by net primary production or by the ingestion of smaller
260 organisms. Instead, individual mass increases in DBEM when anabolism exceeds catabolism,
261 both of which are affected by temperature and other drivers (see Section 2.3). Similar to
262 APECOSM, FEISTY and BOATS, the explicit balance between anabolic and catabolic processes
263 drives an organism's scope for growth—if catabolism outpaces anabolism, an individual's mass
264 will decline. In DBEM, anabolism accelerates more slowly with warming compared to
265 catabolism. Thus, as waters war, an organism's scope for growth becomes increasingly
266 limited, and their maximum size decreases.

267

268 Organisms do not interact in DBEM. Rather, temperature and other forcings drive the spatial
269 distribution of species across the ocean, with species' relative abundance in a region changing
270 with respect to temperature depending on their thermal preference, and the prevailing water
271 temperature. Thus, as waters warm, ecosystem structure changes by individual organisms
272 becoming smaller on average, and by different species shifting their spatial boundaries to
273 follow their thermal preferences.

274

275 Finally, energy transfer from small to large organisms through size-based predation is not the
276 only way that different parts of the ecosystem interact; in APECOSM, BOATS, DBPM, DBEM

277 and FEISTY, energy moves from large to the smallest size classes through reproduction. In
278 these models, the flux of small organism biomass entering the population through
279 reproduction can increase or decrease, depending on the relative impacts of warming on large
280 organisms. In FEISTY for example, if large organisms are more adversely affected by warming
281 than small organisms, the reproduction rate in larger size classes would also decline, leading
282 to less biomass overall.

283

284 **2.2. How do models incorporate lower trophic level processes?**

285 Net primary production sustains essentially all non-photosynthetic life in the oceans, and
286 limits the biomass of higher trophic levels (Chavez et al. 2011). Solar energy captured and
287 organic matter synthesized by primary producers flow through the food webs, primarily by
288 larger organisms preying on smaller organisms. FishMIP models focus on higher trophic levels,
289 so lower trophic level processes are driven by a range of Earth system model forcings (Table
290 1). The role of lower trophic levels in setting the limits to growth for higher trophic levels is
291 represented across the eight FishMIP models in two ways. First, for BOATS, DBEM,
292 Macroecological and Ecotroph, net primary production is used to determine limits of
293 consumer growth rates and total biomass according to trophic transfer functions. Second, in
294 the trait-based models (APECOSM, DBPM, FEISTY and ZoomSS), plankton biomass and export
295 production are consumed by the size classes or functional groups that feed on them. This
296 energy is then transferred to higher trophic levels through size-based predation. However, all
297 eight models considered here are one-way forced (run offline), so there is no feedback from
298 higher trophic levels to lower trophic level biomass or production. This means that for the
299 trait-based models, ingestion-fuelled growth of higher trophic level predators is not explicitly
300 matched by predation mortality in the plankton.

301

302 The correlation of mean phytoplankton size with total primary production is an important
303 driver of ecosystem structure (Boyce et al. 2015). Phytoplankton are generally larger in more
304 productive waters (Barnes et al. 2011; Finkel et al. 2010). Given the size-structured nature of
305 the marine ecosystem (Trebilco et al. 2013), smaller phytoplankton support longer food
306 chains, which are thought to support relatively less consumer biomass (Eddy et al. 2020;
307 Ryther, 1969). All models explicitly represent this phenomenon with the exception of
308 EcoTroph and DBEM. EcoTroph uses trophic level instead of body size to represent the marine
309 ecosystem. In DBEM, changes in net primary production affect the carrying capacity of
310 modelled species disregarding the size of primary producers. In BOATS and Macroecological,
311 changes in food chain length are represented by a varying representative size of
312 phytoplankton, the size increasing with net primary production according to empirical
313 equations. In DBPM and ZooMSS, the phytoplankton size-spectrum, which is the relationship
314 between primary producer abundance N and body size w , $N = aw^b$, is continuous, with the
315 intercept a and slope b set by phytoplankton biomass. In these two models, the plankton size-
316 spectrum intercept is lower and the slope is steeper in less productive waters, meaning
317 relatively more small producers but less biomass overall. APECOSM and FEISTY use size-
318 fractionated phytoplankton and zooplankton biomass inputs from earth system models to
319 directly set the biomass of small and large phytoplankton and zooplankton groups, with a
320 fixed size-spectrum slope assigned to each LTL group in APECOSM. APECOSM and FEISTY also
321 use export carbon to represent detrital flux across the entire water column (in APECOSM) or
322 to the seafloor to fuel the growth of benthic invertebrates (in FEISTY).

323

324

325 **2.3. How do models incorporate other impacts?**

326 All models in the FishMIP ensemble are driven solely by temperature and LTL drivers, with
327 the exception of APECOSM and DBEM (Table 1). In these two models, movement of organisms
328 between adjacent grid cells is resolved, so both models incorporate current speeds. Since
329 APECOSM resolves the 3D density of animal biomass, the model also uses 3D
330 photosynthetically active radiation to resolve water clarity and light penetration across the
331 water column. Thus, in APECOSM areas with the highest consumer biomass are not
332 necessarily regions with the highest LTL biomass, due to active and passive horizontal
333 movements in response to temperature, light, food availability and the strength of currents.
334 Both APECOSM and DBEM also incorporate oxygen concentration, which impacts anabolic
335 processes; lower oxygen concentrations reduces the scope for organism growth in both
336 models, and thus reduces total biomass. DBEM also resolves the negative impacts of
337 acidification on catabolic processes, by incorporating pH forcings. DBEM also uses salinity, sea
338 ice and mixed layer depth forcings, alongside temperature, to establish the spatial extent of
339 each of the >1200 fish and invertebrate species the model resolves.

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348 **Table 1** Summary of temperature, lower trophic level (LTL) and other drivers sourced from
 349 earth system models, used by each model in the FishMIP ensemble, as well as the ecosystem
 350 representation of each model. All drivers used by the models in this experiment had a monthly
 351 temporal resolution.

Model and key references	Temperature drivers	LTL drivers	Other drivers	Taxonomic scope
APECOSM Maury et al. 2007a; 2007b; Maury 2010; Maury and Poggiale, 2013	3D water temperature	3D small and large phytoplankton, 3D small and large zooplankton biomass*, 3D export carbon flux	3D oxygen concentration, 3D photosynthetically active radiation, 3D current velocities	All epipelagic, mesopelagic and migratory heterotrophic marine animals in the pelagic ecosystem between 15µg– 120kg.
BOATS Carozza et al. 2016; 2017	2D water temperature (averaged over top 75 m)	2D depth-integrated net primary production	NA	All commercial animal biomass from 10g–100kg.
DBEM Cheung et al. 2008; 2010; 2011; 2016	2D sea surface temperature	2D depth-integrated net primary production	2D surface and bottom oxygen concentration, salinity and pH, sea ice, mixed layer depth, 3D current velocities	>1200 fish and invertebrate species.
DBPM Blanchard et al. 2009; 2012	2D sea surface and bottom water temperature	2D depth-integrated small and large phytoplankton biomass	NA	All benthic and pelagic marine animals, weighing between 1mg and 1 tonne.
EcoTroph Gascuel and Pauly, 2009; du Pontavice et al. 2020	2D sea surface temperature	2D depth-integrated small and large phytoplankton biomass	NA	All marine animals with trophic level ≥ 2 .
FEISTY Petrik et al. 2019	2D upper pelagic (averaged over 100 m) and bottom water temperature	2D depth-integrated (top 100 m) small and large zooplankton biomass*, 2D export carbon flux to the sea floor	NA	Forage, large pelagic and demersal fish, as well as benthic invertebrates, between 1mg and 125kg.
Macroecological Jennings and Collingridge (2015)	2D sea surface temperature	2D depth-integrated small and large phytoplankton biomass	NA	All marine animals between 1mg and 1 tonne.
ZooMSS Heneghan et al. (2020)	2D sea surface temperature	2D sea surface phytoplankton biomass	NA	Nine zooplankton groups, from flagellates to jellyfish and all fish and mammals between 1mg and 10 tonnes.

352 * Where small and large zooplankton biomass are not provided by an earth system model (as
 353 is the case with CESM1-BGC, the earth system model used in this study) FishMIP splits total
 354 zooplankton biomass using the ratio of small and large phytoplankton biomass.
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Table 2 Summary of temperature and lower trophic level impacts in the FishMIP model ensemble.

Model	Temperature effect on:		Lower trophic level effect on:	
	Individual anabolic and catabolic processes	Ecosystem structure	Individual anabolic and catabolic processes	Ecosystem structure
APECOSM	Ingestion and thus predatory mortality scales with temperature and varies with predator size and the density of prey. Assimilation, maintenance, and non-predation mortality rates also scale with temperature. Temperature effects largely balance where prey density is high. In food limited areas, catabolic processes increase faster than anabolic processes, causing individual mass to decrease.	Growth and mortality increase with temperature. In food limited situations, leading to less biomass, especially for large organisms. In prey rich regions, temperature does not drive biomass down but drives a faster transfer toward large sizes causing an increase in large organisms and a decrease of small organisms due to top-down control.	Small and large plankton biomass is the primary food source of small consumer organisms. More plankton biomass increases satiation and maximizes individual growth and reproduction, thus driving increases in biomass.	More plankton biomass supports more ecosystem biomass and reduces the trophic amplification of food limitation with size. This leads to biomass increase of large organisms and the presence of larger species in the communities.
BOATS	Warming drives higher individual growth and mortality rates, which reduces the maximum biomass that can be supported by a given level of primary production.	Phytoplankton size decreases with warming, lengthening food chains and reducing total energy transferred to higher trophic levels.	Net primary production sets the limits to growth across all body size classes. Higher production means more biomass.	Phytoplankton size decreases with decreasing production. Smaller phytoplankton mean longer food chains causing biomass declines for all sizes.
DBEM	Biomass creation occurs after catabolism is deducted from anabolism. Catabolism increases faster with warming than anabolism. Thus, biomass decreases with warming.	Catabolism increases with size faster than anabolism, so warming affects large species more and drives shifts in spatial distribution of species.	In all regions, net primary production is a key part of what sets the limits to maximum biomass across all higher trophic levels.	Lower net primary production means less consumer biomass can be supported.
DBPM	Ingestion-driven growth, and mortality rates from predation and natural sources scale with temperature at the same rate. Thus, temperature effects largely balance, except in low food regions where natural mortality is relatively large and causes biomass to decrease.	Natural mortality costs scale with temperature but decrease with body size. Thus, warming increases mortality relatively more for small organisms compared to large, potentially causing their biomass to decrease faster.	Small and large phytoplankton biomass set the slope and intercept of the phytoplankton size-spectrum, which is the primary food source of small pelagic organisms. More phytoplankton means more biomass.	Relatively more small phytoplankton with less phytoplankton biomass, which reduces food for small organisms and increases food chain length. Decreases overall biomass, especially for larger sizes, as senescence increases with size.
EcoTroph	Warming drives higher individual turnover rates, and lower trophic transfer efficiency, which means fewer individuals can be supported, causing biomass to decrease.	Trophic transfer efficiency decreases with warming, causing higher trophic level biomass to decrease more than lower trophic level biomass.	Net primary production is a driver of total biomass across all trophic levels. Higher production means more biomass.	Lower net primary production means less biomass can be supported across all trophic levels.
FEISTY	Maintenance costs, ingestion-driven growth, and mortality rates from predation scale with temperature. Maintenance costs increase faster with warming compared to ingestion, so warming reduces the scope for growth, causing biomass to decrease.	Maintenance costs increase faster than ingestion-driven growth with body size and temperature. Thus, warming will reduce the scope for large organism growth more than small organisms.	Zooplankton is food for all small consumers and medium pelagic consumers. Export production fuels benthic growth. More zooplankton biomass and export production means more ecosystem biomass overall.	Less zooplankton biomass, composed of relatively more small zooplankton means more steps in the food chain, possibly reducing large organism biomass more as metabolic costs outpace ingestion.
Macroecological	Warming drives higher individual production rates, which means fewer individuals can be supported by a given level of production, causing total biomass to decrease.	Phytoplankton size decreases with warming, lengthening food chains and reducing how much energy is transferred to higher trophic levels.	Net primary production is a key determinant of total biomass. Higher net primary production means more biomass.	Phytoplankton size decreases with decreasing production. Smaller phytoplankton support longer food chains, thus less biomass across all sizes.
ZooMSS	Ingestion-driven growth and mortality rates from predation and senescence scale with temperature at the same rate. Thus, temperature effects largely balance, except where senescence mortality is large, causing biomass to decrease.	Warming negatively impacts large organisms more than small by increasing senescence. If large organism biomass declines more than small, small biomass will increase from reduced predation.	The phytoplankton spectrum—set by total phytoplankton biomass—is the main food of microzooplankton. More phytoplankton means more consumer biomass.	Less phytoplankton biomass means less food for small organisms, and relatively more small phytoplankton. Drives shifts in zooplankton composition, which stabilise food chain length.

360 **2.4. Experimental protocol**

361 To isolate the impact of temperature and LTL processes on the FishMIP ensemble, we
362 conducted four simulations (Table 3). In each simulation, all models were forced with
363 different combinations of temperature, LTL and other (for APECOSM and DBEM) drivers from
364 pre-industrial, historical and high emissions scenarios (RCP8.5; IPCC, 2014) from the CESM1-
365 BGC earth system model (Harrison et al. 2018). All forcings were provided to modellers with
366 a monthly temporal resolution. We do not use a range (from low to high) of emission
367 scenarios for the future, or source forcings from multiple Earth system models, as our purpose
368 here is to isolate sources of structural uncertainty within the FishMIP model ensemble itself
369 (Payne et al. 2016). Under the RCP8.5 scenario, the CESM1-BGC model projects a global sea
370 surface temperature increase, which is particularly marked at high latitudes (Figure 1b); net
371 primary production declines across most of the tropics and mid-latitudes, but increases at
372 high latitudes and in the eastern South Pacific (Figure 1d); phytoplankton and zooplankton
373 biomass declines across most of the world's oceans, except in polar regions (Figure 1f, h). The
374 mean change in sea surface temperature across the global ocean from 1950 to 2100 under
375 historical (from 1950-2005) and RCP8.5 (from 2006-2100) scenarios is +3.2°C, and for net
376 primary production, phytoplankton and zooplankton carbon the mean change was -14%, -8%
377 and -21%, respectively.

378

379 To enable the model comparison, two standardized outputs - total consumer biomass and the
380 biomass of large consumers (≥ 30 cm; see Tittensor et al. 2018 for details) - were calculated
381 from each ecosystem model. All models supplied both outputs, except DBEM which did not
382 provide the biomass of large consumers. Outputs were reported as depth integrated carbon
383 biomass (g m^{-2}) and aggregated to a spatial grid with a resolution of 1° on a monthly or annual

384 time step, depending on model capability. Owing to differences in model formulation total
 385 consumer biomass varies widely amongst models, all else being equal (Tittensor et al. 2018).
 386 Since our focus was not on explaining these differences in total biomass, but rather the
 387 differences in the responses of the models to temperature and LTL changes, we compared
 388 model outputs using biomass change relative to biomass levels under the preindustrial
 389 control. Further, as our focus was isolating impacts of temperature and LTL processes,
 390 simulations were run in the absence of fishing.

391

392 Forcing data from the CESM1-BGC model used for this protocol, and all model outputs
 393 presented here are available on the ISIMIP servers (<https://www.isimip.org/>).

394

395 **Table 3** Summary of the experimental simulations and corresponding environmental driver
 396 combinations. Temperature: all temperature-related drivers (e.g., sea surface temperature);
 397 LTL: all lower trophic level drivers (e.g., phytoplankton biomass); Other: any drivers that are
 398 not related to temperature or lower trophic levels (e.g., pH). The abbreviations for forcings
 399 are: PI (blue) = pre-industrial control, H (yellow) = historical, RCP85 (purple) = RCP8.5.

	<u>Simulation</u>							
	Control		Temperature Change		LTL Change		All (Climate) Change	
<u>Drivers</u>	<u>1950-2005</u>	<u>2006-2100</u>	<u>1950-2005</u>	<u>2006-2100</u>	<u>1950-2005</u>	<u>2006-2100</u>	<u>1950-2005</u>	<u>2006-2100</u>
Temperature	PI	PI	H	RCP85	PI	PI	H	RCP85
LTL	PI	PI	PI	PI	H	RCP85	H	RCP85
Other	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	H	RCP85

400

401

403

404 **Figure 1** Control (historical averaged over 1950-1960) forcing variables and the change in

405 those variables from climate change (RCP8.5) from the CESM1-BGC earth system model; a,b)

406 Sea surface temperature, c,d) Net primary production, e,f) Phytoplankton carbon, g,h)

407 Zooplankton carbon. The change in each variable is measured as the mean over 2090-2100

408 under the RCP8.5 scenario minus the mean over 1950-1960 (for sea surface temperature), or

409 the percentage change between the mean in 1950-1960 and 2090-2100 (for net primary

410 production, phytoplankton carbon and zooplankton carbon).

411

412

413 **3. Results**

414 **3.1. Global changes in total consumer biomass**

415 All models projected a decline of global consumer biomass in the Temperature Change
416 simulation, with the exception of APECOSM (Figure 2a). The spread of total consumer biomass
417 change in response to warming ranged from around -35% for Macroecological and BOATS, to
418 +3% for APECOSM by the end of the 21st century. EcoTroph produced the third largest change
419 after BOATS and Macroecological of around -13%. The remaining four models (DBEM, DBPM,
420 FEISTY, ZooMSS) simulated modest changes in consumer biomass of between -2% (FEISTY) to
421 -7% (DBPM) in response to changes in temperature alone.

422

423 The LTL Change simulation also showed biomass decreases for most models, except BOATS
424 and Macroecological, which projected biomass increases (Figure 2b). For these two models,
425 the trajectory of biomass change was switched in the LTL Change simulation from negative
426 change to positive in comparison with the warming only simulation. In contrast, APECOSM
427 projected consumer biomass to increase slightly with warming, but decrease with LTL
428 changes. APECOSM projected a 7% decrease in total consumer biomass globally, while BOATS
429 and Macroecological projected increases of 10-15% in response to LTL changes in isolation.
430 Maximum decreases of biomass in LTL simulations are half the magnitude (up to 15%) of the
431 decreases in warming simulations. The smallest response to LTL changes was from EcoTroph,
432 which projected a total consumer biomass change of <-1%. Trends in total consumer biomass
433 from the other five models (DBEM, DBPM, FEISTY and ZooMSS) were grouped within a range
434 between -5% (DBEM) and -15% (ZooMSS).

435

436 The combined temperature and LTL changes led to a decline in consumer biomass across all
437 models except DBEM (Figure 2c). By the end of the 21st century, changes in consumer
438 biomass in the All (Climate) Change simulation ranged from around -30% for BOATS and
439 Macroecological, to +3% for DBEM. The other five models (APECOSM, DBPM, EcoTroph,
440 FEISTY and ZooMSS) had changes in total consumer biomass of between -5% (for APECOSM)
441 and -17% (for ZooMSS). For all models except BOATS, DBEM and Macroecological, climate
442 change impacts at the global scale were largely the sum of the separate global impacts of
443 warming and LTL change, with almost no non-additive impact (Figure 2d). For BOATS and
444 Macroecological, climate change impacts caused total consumer biomass to decline by about
445 4% more than the sum of separate warming and LTL impacts. In DBEM, total consumer
446 biomass under climate change was ~15% higher than under the combined, separate impacts
447 of warming and LTL impacts, indicating some non-additive impact of cumulative temperature
448 and LTL changes. Non-additive impacts in DBEM may also be caused by additional impacts
449 from changes in pH and oxygen levels. APECOSM, the only other model to incorporate non-
450 temperature or LTL drivers, had negligible non-additive impacts, indicating these other drivers
451 had little effect compared to warming and LTL shifts.

452

453

Figure 2 Model projections of percentage change in global consumer biomass, relative to the Control, from 1950-2100 for the: a) Temperature Change simulation, b) Lower Trophic Level (LTL) Change simulation, c) All (Climate) Change simulation and d) the non-additive impacts of temperature and LTL changes, calculated by taking the difference between the All Change and the sum of the Temperature and LTL Change simulations.

3.2. Spatial changes in total consumer biomass

Globally averaged time-series of total consumer biomass change conceal considerable spatial variation across regions, and between models in each experiment. Temperature-induced shifts in the spatial distribution of total consumer biomass (Figure 3, left column) varied from

465 increases in many regions for APECOSM, to decreases across the global ocean in DBPM,
466 ZooMSS, EcoTroph, BOATS and Macroecological. The magnitude of the total consumer
467 biomass changes generally followed the magnitude of change in temperature (Figure 1b);
468 temperate regions that experienced the strongest warming (Figure 1b) exhibited the largest
469 decreases in biomass for these five models. FEISTY and ZooMSS consumer biomass also
470 decreased with increased temperature in many of the regions with the greatest warming.
471 However, in warm regions (Figure 1a) with relatively small temperature increases such as the
472 eastern Pacific or northern Indian Ocean, FEISTY consumer biomass increased, and small
473 increases in ZooMSS consumer biomass occurred almost entirely in very high latitude polar
474 regions where temperature change was relatively small (Figure 1b). In contrast, APECOSM
475 consumer biomass increased across most of the global ocean in response to warming. The
476 exception to this pattern was in patches where phytoplankton biomass was highest (Figure
477 1c) such as the North Atlantic, the Bering Strait or the South Pacific around New Zealand. In
478 DBEM, temperature-induced changes in consumer biomass were greatest in the warmest
479 waters around the equator, where DBEM consumer biomass decreased by 60-100%. In cold
480 high latitude waters, DBEM consumer biomass increased by $\geq 60\%$ in response to warming.

481

482 For all models, lower trophic level (LTL) induced shifts in the distribution of consumer biomass
483 (Figure 3, centre column) show more agreement in their patterns of change; most models
484 show biomass decreases in equatorial regions, and increases towards the poles. The
485 exceptions here are APECOSM, FEISTY and ZooMSS which show a mix of positive and negative
486 consumer biomass toward the north pole. Consumer biomass shifts generally followed
487 changes in the distribution of the main LTL forcings used by each model (Figure 1d, f, h).
488 APECOSM, DBPM, FEISTY and ZooMSS use plankton biomass inputs (Table 2), and for these

489 models, consumer biomass generally decreased with decreasing phytoplankton carbon
490 (Figure 1f) and increases were isolated to polar regions. DBEM, EcoTroph, BOATS and
491 Macroecological use net primary production as their LTL forcing and the spatial distribution
492 of changes in consumer biomass followed spatial shifts in net primary production (Figure 1d),
493 with increases in biomass not only in polar regions, but also in the North Pacific and in the
494 south east Pacific.

495

496 When both temperature and LTL drivers changed simultaneously in the All (Climate) Change
497 simulation, shifts in the distribution of consumer biomass for each model were a combination
498 of the shifts driven by separate temperature and LTL effects (Figure 3, right column;
499 Supplementary Figure S1). Across all models, temperature-induced declines in consumer
500 biomass were generally exacerbated in regions where LTL changes negatively impacted
501 consumer biomass. Overall, consumer biomass generally increased in polar waters, where all
502 LTL variables increased but temperature changed relatively little. Increases in consumer
503 biomass in DBEM were greater in polar regions under climate change, compared to the sum
504 of the separate impacts of warming and LTL shifts (Supplementary Figure S1e). Outside of
505 polar regions, the magnitude and direction of change in consumer biomass varied among
506 models, depending on their individual responses to temperature and LTL changes. For BOATS
507 and Macroecological, the magnitude of positive and negative changes in consumer biomass
508 from LTL shifts in isolation were attenuated when combined with the impacts of warming in
509 the Climate Change simulation (Supplementary Figure S1g, h), however these non-additive
510 effects largely cancelled at the global scale (Figure 2d).

511

512

513 **Figure 3** Maps of relative total consumer biomass averaged over 2090-2100, compared to the
 514 Control, for the Temperature (left column), Lower Trophic Level (LTL) and All Change

515 simulations for a-c) APECOSM, d-f) FEISTY, g-i) ZoomSS, j-l) DBPM, m-o) DBEM, p-r) EcoTroph,
516 s-u) BOATS, v-x) Macroecological. Maps are ordered by the magnitude (from smallest to
517 greatest) of the negative warming impact on consumer biomass.

518

519 **3.3. Disentangling temperature and lower trophic level impacts on total consumer** 520 **biomass**

521 Figure 4 compares the forced changes in sea surface temperature with the co-located
522 simulated changes in biomass for all grid cells in the global ocean. Regressions give negative
523 exponential slopes for all models, but with substantial variation (Supplementary Table S1).
524 Globally, consumer biomass changed between -0.5% and -2.0% for every 1°C of sea surface
525 warming for APECOSM, FEISTY, DBPM and ZoomSS, and between -4.8% and -15.4% per 1°C
526 across EcoTroph, BOATS and Macroecological (Supplementary Table S4). The models vary in
527 their degree of linearity, with DBEM projecting the greatest nonlinearity in the impacts of
528 warming between cold and warm waters (Figure 4e; Supplementary Table S4). DBEM
529 consumer biomass increased by ~50% in cold waters (<15°C waters) in response to warming
530 (Figure 4e), and decreased on average by >27% for each 1°C warming in warm ($\geq 15^\circ\text{C}$ waters)
531 waters.

532

533 Figure 5 shows the corresponding plots for LTL forcing. For all models, changes in total
534 consumer biomass were positively correlated with changes in their respective aggregated
535 lower trophic level (LTL) forcing (Figure 5). A 1% change in LTL forcings caused a change in
536 total consumer biomass of between 0.6% in DBPM to 1.7% in BOATS (Supplementary Table
537 S4). Positive correlations between consumer biomass and LTL changes ranged from $r = 0.39$
538 for DBPM, to $r = 0.98$ for EcoTroph. For all models except DBPM, the greatest correlation

539 was between change in total consumer biomass and change in total LTL production, or
 540 biomass, of the model's chosen LTL forcing (Supplementary Table S3). In models that used
 541 size-fractionated LTL inputs, or additional secondary LTL inputs, changes in consumer biomass
 542 were less correlated with changes in their main aggregated LTL forcing (APECOSM, DBPM,
 543 FEISTY) compared to models that did not use size-fractionated or multiple LTL forcings
 544 (BOATS, DBEM, EcoTroph, Macroecological, ZooMSS).
 545

546
 547 **Figure 4** Change in total consumer biomass (%) against the mean change in sea surface
 548 temperature (SST) over 2090-2100, for individual 1° grid squares, under the Temperature

549 Change simulation, compared to the Control simulation, for a) APECOSM, b) FEISTY, c)
550 ZooMSS, d) DBPM, e) DBEM, f) EcoTroph, g) BOATS, h) Macroecological. Each point is coloured
551 according to the mean 1950-1960 historical SST in its grid cell. Dotted horizontal and vertical
552 black lines indicate where % change in total consumer biomass and change in temperature
553 are zero, respectively. The green line is the fitted regression (Δ Total Consumer Biomass =
554 $\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \Delta \text{SST}) + \varepsilon$) for the change in consumer biomass with warming. We use
555 exponential regression to calculate the line of best fit here since all models incorporate
556 temperature effects using an exponential function (see Supplementary Information).
557 Information about the fitted regression is in Supplementary Table S1 and S4.
558

559

560 **Figure 5** Change in total consumer biomass (%) against change in aggregated lower trophic
 561 level forcings (LTL), from 2090-2100 under the LTL Change simulation, against the Control, for
 562 individual 1° grid squares, compared to the Control simulation for a) APECOSM, b) FEISTY, c)
 563 ZooMSS, d) DBPM, e) DBEM, f) EcoTroph, g) BOATS, h) Macroecological, with Pearson's
 564 correlation coefficient (r) reported for each. Each point is coloured according to the average
 565 1950-1960 historical sea surface temperature (SST) in its corresponding grid cell. The black
 566 solid line is the 1:1 line, and the dotted horizontal and vertical black lines indicate where %
 567 change in total consumer biomass and % change in LTL are zero, respectively. The green line
 568 is the fitted regression (Δ Total Consumer Biomass = $\beta_0 + \beta_1\Delta$ LTL + ϵ) for the change in

569 consumer biomass with warming. For models that use more than one LTL variable
570 (APECOSM), or size-fractionated LTL (FEISTY and DBPM), Δ LTL is calculated from the sum of
571 all LTL forcings. Information about the fitted regression is in Supplementary Table S2 and S4.

572

573 **3.4. Impacts of warming and lower trophic level change on ecosystem structure**

574 In response to warming, there was little consensus in the relative change of small (<30 cm)
575 and large (\geq 30 cm) consumer biomass (Figure 6a), with four models (BOATS, EcoTroph,
576 Macroecological, ZooMSS) showing a decrease of both and the other three models
577 (APECOSM, DBPM, FEISTY) showing a mixture of responses. Small consumer biomass
578 increased by \sim 2% in both APECOSM and FEISTY in response to warming, but large consumer
579 biomass increased in APECOSM by 5% while decreasing in FEISTY by $>$ 10%. Similarly, although
580 small consumer biomass in DBPM and ZooMSS decreased by 3% and 6% respectively, these
581 models disagreed on the direction of change for large consumer biomass. In response to
582 warming total large consumer biomass in DBPM increased by 15%, and even up to 60% in
583 some regions (Supplementary Figure S2n), but ZooMSS total large consumer biomass declined
584 by \sim 2% overall. Finally, small and large consumer biomass declined in EcoTroph, BOATS and
585 Macroecological, and the spatial pattern of decline across these models was similar
586 (Supplementary Figure S2). There was no difference in the magnitude of the decline of small
587 and large consumer biomass in Macroecological, however in EcoTroph and BOATS the
588 magnitude of the decline in large consumer biomass was greater than the decline in small
589 consumer biomass.

590

591 Changes in total small and large consumer biomass in response to lower trophic level (LTL)
592 changes show more agreement (Figure 6b). The change in total small and large consumer

593 biomass was similar in APECOSM, FEISTY, ZooMSS, EcoTroph, BOATS and Macroecological,
594 and again the spatial pattern of change in small and large consumer biomass generally
595 followed each model's respective LTL forcings (Supplementary Figure S2; Figure 1f-h).
596 However in DBPM, total large consumer biomass declined by 40%, while small consumer
597 biomass declined by only 10%. Large consumer biomass in DBPM varied by over $\pm 60\%$ in
598 some regions, whereas small consumer biomass varied by $<25\%$ across the global ocean
599 (Supplementary Figure S2 o,p).

600

601 Small and large consumer biomass declined for all models (except DBEM, which was excluded
602 from this part of the analysis since it did not provide size-fractionated biomass) in response
603 to climate change (simultaneous temperature and LTL changes) impacts (Figure 6c). Large
604 consumer biomass declined more than small consumer biomass in BOATS, DBPM, EcoTroph
605 and FEISTY. In contrast, small consumer biomass declined more than large consumer biomass
606 in APECOSM and ZooMSS, and there was no difference between small and large consumer
607 biomass change in Macroecological. For all models, the impacts of climate change on small
608 and large consumers were largely the sum of temperature and LTL impacts, with relatively
609 small non-additive impacts (Figure 6d).

610

611

612 **Figure 6** Change in total small (<30 cm) consumer biomass versus change in global large
 613 (>30cm) consumer biomass averaged between 2090-2100 relative to Control simulation for
 614 each model (excluding DBEM, which did not provide small and large consumer biomass) in
 615 the a) Temperature Change simulation b) Lower Trophic Level (LTL) Change simulation, c) All
 616 Change simulation and d) the non-additive impacts of temperature and LTL changes,
 617 calculated by taking the difference between the All Change and the sum of the Temperature
 618 and LTL Change simulations. The red solid line is the 1:1 line, and the dotted horizontal and
 619 vertical black lines indicate where the percentage change in global large and small consumer
 620 biomass are zero, respectively.

621

622

623 **4. Discussion**

624 The results of our experimental protocol reveal commonalities, as well as contrasts among
625 the FishMIP models. All models agreed that the combination of warming and lower trophic
626 level (LTL) shifts will cause substantial regional changes in consumer biomass. Furthermore,
627 no model projected a significant increase in global biomass in response to climate change.
628 However, the impacts of warming varied markedly between models, leading to large inter-
629 model disagreements. Changes in LTL drivers were more directly correlated with the
630 outcomes on consumer biomass, but with substantial variation among models. For almost all
631 models, the combined impacts of warming and LTL changes were largely additive at the global
632 scale, showing little nonlinear interaction, and additional climate change drivers (e.g. oxygen,
633 acidification, current speeds) were not significant global drivers in the models that included
634 them (APECOSM and DBEM). By separating the marine ecosystem model responses to
635 climate-driven warming versus LTL shifts, our results point toward the processes that need to
636 be clarified to reduce the uncertainty of how these two dominant drivers impact marine
637 ecosystems.

638

639 **4.1. Warming impacts are complex**

640 One straightforward expectation might be that the different responses to warming reflect
641 differences in the temperature scalings used in each model. However, the differences in
642 temperature scalings do not readily explain the variation in the results. For instance, DBPM
643 and Macroecological use identical temperature scalings (see Supplementary Information S2.4
644 and S2.7), yet DBPM's projections of warming-induced biomass decline are almost an order
645 of magnitude smaller than those of Macroecological. This does not mean the temperature
646 scalings are irrelevant, but rather that the emergent results depend on the interactions of

647 multiple temperature-dependent processes, operating within the structural context of each
648 model.

649

650 For example, DBEM attempts to resolve preferred temperature ranges for different species,
651 while the other models consider the effect of temperature on generalized physiological
652 processes, implicitly assuming that species moving out of a region are replaced by species
653 moving in with no change in ecosystem function. Although food web processes are not
654 included in the DBEM species-distribution model, it projects an emptying of tropical waters
655 and a corresponding build-up of biomass in polar waters, as species move poleward to follow
656 their thermal preferences. This redistribution of the biomass of >1200 recorded commercial
657 species included in the model reflects the absence of very warm water fish that can
658 repopulate the tropics, and the small number of cold water fish in the initial state (Cheung et
659 al. 2010). It also largely explains the model's combined impacts of warming, LTL shifts and
660 other drivers being nonlinear: relative to extant species in polar waters, a larger number of
661 species follow their thermal niche poleward and are able to take advantage of increased
662 primary production in high latitude regions, compared to the regions they left behind.

663

664 DBEM aside, four of the models included here (APECOSM, DBPM, FEISTY and ZooMSS) project
665 much smaller warming impacts on consumer biomass than the remaining three
666 models (BOATS, EcoTroph and Macroecological). Although there are many differences
667 between these models, one particularly salient feature is that the low-sensitivity models all
668 use LTL biomass as Earth-system model (ESM) drivers for the projections, together with
669 temperature-dependent feeding rates. In contrast, the high-sensitivity models use ESM net
670 primary production to directly limit the growth rates of upper trophic levels. We suggest that

671 the discrepancy in temperature sensitivity between these two model groups can be
672 attributed, at least in part, to an inconsistency that arises from the 1-way forcing of marine
673 models with LTL biomass. The relationship between LTL biomass (B_{LTL}), LTL production (P_{LTL})
674 and higher trophic level predation ($Pred_{HTL}$) through time t can be represented as:

$$675 \quad \frac{dB_{LTL}}{dt} = P_{LTL}(t) - Pred_{HTL}(t).$$

676 In reality, if warming accelerates predation rates, but lower trophic level production remains
677 constant or does not increase as much, such that $P_{LTL}(t) < Pred_{HTL}(t)$, LTL biomass would
678 decrease. However in the 1-way forcing used here, LTL biomass is determined externally by
679 the Earth system model and is not affected by predation from higher trophic levels. Thus,
680 increased predation rates from warming on fixed LTL biomass causes an increase in the flux
681 of biomass energy into higher trophic levels that is decoupled from lower trophic level
682 production. This increased energy input counters the increased metabolic rates and
683 associated respiratory losses, dampening biomass declines from warming. This inconsistency
684 in coupling between LTLs and higher trophic level consumers would tend towards an
685 underestimate of warming impacts on consumer biomass. In contrast, in the production-
686 driven models there is no spurious energy input under warming, so that the respiration cost
687 acts alone to drive biomass down strongly.

688

689 Our results also explored the warming impacts on ecosystem structure, defined as the relative
690 biomass of small versus large organisms. Here, there was little consensus between models.
691 DBPM and FEISTY provide a striking example of divergent projections of ecosystem structure
692 with warming. In DBPM, ingestion-fuelled anabolism outpaces senescence-induced mortality
693 in large organisms as waters warm (Blanchard et al. 2012), causing their biomass to increase.

694 This raises predation pressure on smaller organisms, which when coupled with warming-
695 induced increases in natural mortality, causes their biomass to decline. By contrast, in FEISTY,
696 biomass respiration increases faster with both body size and temperature compared to
697 ingestion-fuelled anabolism (Petrik et al. 2019) reducing the scope for growth and causing
698 large organism biomass to decline with warming. Declines in large consumer biomass in
699 FEISTY with increasing temperature relieve predation pressure on small consumers, resulting
700 in an increase in their biomass, especially in tropical waters. The divergent impacts of warming
701 on individual processes and ecosystem structure reflects the lack of consensus among
702 modellers of how temperature impacts on individuals translate into ecosystem impacts.

703

704 **4.2. Lower trophic level impacts are influenced by choice of forcing**

705 The choice of LTL forcings differed, with each model using either biomass or production
706 variables at the phytoplankton or zooplankton level, with significant impacts on the results.
707 Generally, spatial changes in consumer biomass were most correlated with changes in the
708 distribution of the LTL forcing used. The sensitivity of models to the choice of LTL forcing
709 indicates a lack of common understanding of how to link lower trophic levels production with
710 higher trophic levels, with no consensus on whether production rates or standing-stock
711 biomass should be used. We believe this problem fundamentally arises out of practical
712 necessity because of each model's one-way, offline coupling with the Earth system model—
713 were higher trophic levels and LTLs to be fully coupled, and predation feedbacks onto the LTL
714 resolved, there should be no disagreement on theoretical grounds. However, in the absence
715 of two-way coupled models in the FishMIP ensemble, the development of which is a
716 tremendous technical challenge (see Aumont et al., 2018), this problem remains to be

717 addressed. As mentioned above, this problem also leads to inconsistency in the temperature
718 response when plankton biomass versus net primary production rates are used.

719

720 Ecosystem structure did not change substantially in response to LTL changes, except in DBPM.

721 Large organism biomass in DBPM declined by 40% and small organisms declined by <10% in

722 response to decreases in phytoplankton biomass and resultant shifts in the size structure of

723 the phytoplankton abundance spectrum. DBPM's relatively large decrease in large consumer

724 biomass in response to phytoplankton biomass declines is a result of biomass destruction

725 through senescence mortality, which increases with body size but does not depend on food

726 density, outpacing ingestion-fuelled biomass creation. The other predation-explicit models—

727 including ZoomSS and FEISTY, which also include biomass destruction processes independent

728 of food density that increase with body size—did not exhibit similar declines in large organism

729 biomass. This is because in these models, ingestion-fuelled growth outpaces biomass

730 destruction from these processes, highlighting the sensitivity of model outputs to the

731 parameterisation of these rates. In fact, across all models except DBPM, the change in large

732 organism biomass with LTL change was equal to or slightly less than the change in small

733 organism biomass.

734

735 **4.3. Cumulative warming and lower trophic level impacts are largely additive**

736 Across the model ensemble, climate change impacts on total consumer biomass and

737 ecosystem structure were generally well-approximated by the sum of separate warming and

738 LTL impacts. This lack of non-linearity is perhaps less surprising for the majority of models that

739 only use temperature and LTL drivers to force their models (Tittensor et al. 2018), but

740 remarkably it also holds for APECOSM, which incorporates other drivers such as oxygen, pH

741 and current velocity. The fact that the overall climate change impact on consumer biomass in
742 APECOSM was close to the sum of temperature and LTL impacts indicates that the additional
743 forcings have a comparatively small effect. DBEM, which also includes additional
744 environmental drivers, did show a much stronger non-additive impact of climate change on
745 overall consumer biomass, but this appeared to be driven primarily by the relocation of
746 species niches in DBEM in response to warming, rather than the other drivers. DBEM aside,
747 only BOATS and Macroecological show significant non-linear interactions between
748 temperature and LTL drivers. This can be attributed to the fact that, in BOATS and
749 Macroecological, the representative size of phytoplankton used to force the models scales
750 with both net primary production and temperature, increasing in cooler waters or regions
751 with high net primary production (Dunne et al. 2005). For these two models, the spatial
752 pattern of attenuation follows shifts in net primary production, indicating that warming
753 attenuates the increases and decreases in biomass from shifts in net primary production.

754

755 It may be tempting to assume that the lack of nonlinear interactions in the models means that
756 such nonlinearities are unlikely to exist in the ocean. However, an increasing number of
757 experimental and observational studies indicate that cumulative impacts from climate change
758 stressors such as warming, deoxygenation and acidification are likely to be nonlinear and
759 amplifying (Sampaio and Rosa, 2020). Rather, given the rudimentary representation of many
760 ecosystem processes in the models (e.g. no phenological or diversity-related mechanisms,
761 simplistic or absent predation relationships), we suggest that it is more appropriate to ascribe
762 the lack of nonlinear interactions in marine climate change projections to our present lack of
763 ability to resolve them in the models.

764

765 **4.4. Improving marine ecosystem models with observational constraints**

766 In this study, we have identified key sources of structural uncertainty that drive disparate
767 projections of climate change impacts on the global marine ecosystem. As a first step, the
768 marine modelling community can work to reduce this structural uncertainty and increase the
769 credibility of ecosystem projections by constraining models with independent observations.
770 An increasingly popular approach to confront model projections with observations is to use
771 emergent constraints, which relate the long-term climate sensitivity of an observable
772 ecosystem feature - such as total biomass change (Free et al. 2019) or size-spectrum slope
773 (Blanchard et al. 2017; Heneghan et al. 2019) - to its short-term, observed variability (Allen &
774 Ingram, 2002; Eyring et al. 2019). Models that give a closer fit to short-term observed
775 variability of an ecosystem feature are hypothesised to provide more reliable projections of
776 its long-term variability from climate change (Kwiatkowski et al. 2017; Veytia et al. 2020).
777 Moreover, within a model ensemble, each model's weighting can be linked to its ability to
778 capture the emergent constraint (Eyring et al. 2019). This provides a more sophisticated and
779 credible way to weight model projections within an ensemble, over the standard approach
780 where all models are given equal weighting (known as model democracy), irrespective of
781 performance (Knutti, 2010). Emergent constraints do not require or necessarily reward any
782 particular ecosystem representation. This is important as differing representations of the
783 marine ecosystem across the FishMIP ensemble not only represent our present uncertainty
784 of the most important drivers structuring marine ecosystems, but also the diversity of
785 purpose and scope for which models have been built.

786

787 Finally, it is possible for models to perform well against whole-ecosystem emergent
788 constraints, while neglecting fundamental physiological or ecosystem processes (Knutti,

789 2010). Therefore, if we are to improve marine models, it is also necessary to consider
790 observational constraints on physiological processes such as the balance between growth and
791 respiration with temperature, or ecosystem processes such as the coupling of lower and
792 higher trophic levels. Improving our understanding of how physiological processes such as
793 ingestion and metabolism respond to warming, and how changes in LTL processes propagate
794 through marine ecosystems, are critical steps towards model improvement and more robust
795 climate impact projections.

796

797 **5. Concluding remarks**

798 Projecting the global impact of climate change on marine ecosystems and fisheries is an
799 important and challenging task. Marine ecosystem models represent the current
800 understanding of how climate change could impact the food web and fisheries globally in the
801 future. Yet, although these models have made great strides in recent years, our results show
802 that the current understanding falls short in many respects.

803

804 Our harmonized experimental protocol clearly showed that the responses to the two most
805 important drivers of change – warming and LTL shifts – differ widely among models.
806 Uncertainty in the temperature sensitivities of competing processes, including both
807 physiology and ecological interactions, undermine confidence in the emergent sensitivities,
808 and can only be improved with better observational constraints. Meanwhile, the outcome of
809 changes in both water temperature and LTL production depend strongly on the feedback of
810 consumers on the LTL biomass itself, a process which is not captured by any of the one-way
811 forcings available at present, and can only be rectified with fully two-way coupling, which is
812 itself sure to raise many new questions.

813

814 What are the implications of our results for single ecosystem model studies? The eight models
815 used here differ significantly in their design and ecosystem representation, having been built
816 for different purposes (Tittensor et al. 2018). Although using common outputs across models
817 has been useful here to identify shared weaknesses, this approach conceals the strengths of
818 individual models to resolve certain processes and ecosystem components that other models
819 do not. Thus, studies that explore the unique strengths and weaknesses of individual models
820 remain important, to explore questions that each model has been designed to address.
821 However, results of these single model studies should be interpreted within the greater
822 context of sources of structural uncertainty shared across models, which have been identified
823 here.

824

825 Attempting to summarise the vast complexity of the global marine ecosystem in a handful of
826 equations is enormously difficult. The fact that independently-constructed models with
827 contrasting architectures have arrived at many similar conclusions is encouraging, while their
828 diversity is useful to identify common weaknesses. These initial results from the FishMIP
829 ensemble provide a glimpse into the great promise of multi-model comparisons to improve
830 our understanding of the global marine ecosystem and its future under change.

831

832 **Code and data availability**

833 The experimental protocol is described in this paper but has not code associated with it.
834 Forcing data from CMIP5 used for the protocol, and the FishMIP model outputs presented in
835 this paper are available on the ISIMIP servers ([https://www.isimip.org/gettingstarted/#how-](https://www.isimip.org/gettingstarted/#how-to-join-isimip)
836 [to-join-isimip](https://www.isimip.org/gettingstarted/#how-to-join-isimip)).

837 **Author contributions**

838 JLB, TDE, EDG and DPT led the conceptualisation and development of the protocol for this
839 study, with contributions from the other authors. CH and RFH obtained and processed
840 forcings for the modellers to complete the protocol, with assistance from JV. Model
841 simulations were conducted by RFH, NB, CB, WC, MC, TDE, ME, JAG, DF, JG, OM, JP, CMP,
842 HdP, JS, TCT, PAW. RFH conducted the analysis, with assistance from EDG and JLB. RFH led
843 the writing of the text, with feedback and contributions from all authors.

844

845 **Competing interests**

846 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

847

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